

SUDDEN HEART DEATH COMORBIDITY, FEATURES, DANGERS AND CONSEQUENCES

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Anotation: Sudden heart death (SCD) - a natural, nonviolent death from heart causes, which occurred within an hour after the onset of sudden acute symptoms, most often from ventricle taxiaritis (ventricle fibrillation).As material for scientific work, 247 patients were taken from the Khmer Rouge Regional Emergency Medical Center with nostalgia stenosis, heart ischemic disease, and abdominal fibrillation in the department of emergency cardiology at the Khmer Rouge Regional Emergency Medical Center.

Sudden cardiac death (SCD) is mainly a common death in people with chronic cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Patients with acute miocardial infarction, It is considered to be a sudden death, approved, heart attack death, especially in the first hours of infarction development (in the early (acute) stage of miocardial infarction. According to its mechanisms, clinical appearance and a set of necessary rehabilitation measures, this is fully consistent with sudden heart death that develops in other forms of cardiovascular disease

Keywords: Sudden heart death (SCD), abdominal fibrillation, heart ischemic disease, acute miocardial infarction, heart attack, arterial hypertension, aorta stenosis, cardiogenic shock, left abdominal hypertrophy.

КОМОРБИДНОСТЬ ВНЕЗАПНОЙ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ СМЕРТИ, ОСОБЕННОСТИ, ОПАСНОСТИ И ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ

Аннотация: Внезапная сердечная смерть (ВСС) – естественная, ненасильственная смерть от сердечных причин, наступившая в течение часа после появления внезапных острых симптомов, чаще всего от желудочкового таксирита (мерцательной аритмии). Материалом для научной работы послужили

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247 больных. взят из Регионального центра неотложной медицинской помощи «красных кхмеров» с ностальбическим стенозом, ишемической болезнью сердца и мерцательной аритмией в отделении неотложной кардиологии Регионального центра неотложной медицинской помощи «красных кхмеров».

Внезапная сердечная смерть (ВСС) в основном является распространенной смертью у людей с хроническими сердечно-сосудистыми и респираторными заболеваниями. У больных острым инфарктом миокарда внезапной смертью считается смерть от сердечного приступа, особенно в первые часы развития инфаркта (в ранней (острой) стадии инфаркта миокарда). По ее механизмам, клинической картине и комплекс необходимых реабилитационных мероприятий, что полностью соответствует внезапной сердечной смерти, развивающейся при других формах сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний

Ключевые слова: внезапная сердечная смерть (ВСС), фибрилляция брюшной полости, ишемическая болезнь сердца, острый инфаркт миокарда, инфаркт, артериальная гипертензия, стеноз аорты, кардиогенный шок, гипертрофия левой части живота.

YURAK KO'RINIY O'LIMI XUSUSIYATLARI, XUSUSIYATLARI, XAVFLARI VA OQIBATLARI

Annotatsiya: To'satdan yurak o'limi (SCD) - to'satdan o'tkir simptomlar boshlanganidan keyin bir soat ichida sodir bo'lgan yurak sabablaridan tabiiy, zo'ravonliksiz o'lim, ko'pincha qorincha taksiariti (qorincha fibrilatsiyasi). Ilmiy ish uchun material sifatida 247 bemor olindi. Khmer Rouge mintaqaviy shoshilinch tibbiy yordam markazidan nostalbiya stenozi, yurak ishemik kasalligi va qorin fibrilatsiyasi bilan Khmer Rouge mintaqaviy shoshilinch tibbiy yordam markazining shoshilinch kardiologiya bo'limida olingan.

To'satdan yurak o'limi (SCD) asosan surunkali yurak-qon tomir va nafas olish kasalliklari bilan og'rigan odamlarda keng tarqalgan o'limdir. O'tkir miokard infarkti bo'lgan bemorlar, Bu to'satdan o'lim hisoblanadi, tasdiqlangan, yurak xuruji o'lim, ayniqsa, infarkt rivojlanishining birinchi soatlarida (miokard infarktining erta (o'tkir) bosqichida. Uning mexanizmlariga ko'ra, klinik ko'rinish va a. zarur reabilitatsiya choralari majmuasi, bu yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining boshqa shakllarida rivojlanadigan to'satdan yurak o'limiga to'liq mos keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: To'satdan yurak o'limi (KKD), qorin fibrilatsiyasi, yurak ishemik kasalligi, o'tkir miokard infarkti, yurak xuruji, arterial gipertenziya, aorta stenoz, kardiogen shok, chap qorin bo'shlig'i gipertrofiyasi.

Research materials and methods: Nostalgable abuse stenosis, heart ischemic disease, abdominal fibrillysis in the Department of Emergency Cardiology of the Khmer Rouge Regional Emergency Medical Center from 17.08.2022 to 12.04.2024 as material of scientific work 247 patients who applied for diagnosis were taken. The age figure for patients was between 48 and 87 years old in men, their average age was 71.25, in women it was between 52 and 74 years old, and the average age figure was $66.18 \pm 1.1 \pm 1.4$. Since then, 169 (68.42%) of the patients were men and 78 (31.57%) were women. The diagnosis was based on patients' complaints when they arrived at the hospital, objective examination, anemia of the disease, as well as paraclinic information.

Sudden cardiac death (SCD)

1. Patients with Miocard's infarction anemia, especially those with cardiomedomedia and chronic heart failure.
2. Patients with coronial heart disease with high levels of abdominal arrhythmia
3. Patients with corniary heart disease who have several main risk factors: arterial hypertension, left ventricle hypertrophy, smoking, carbohydrate and fat metabolism, etc.
4. Patients with any heart disease who have severe miocardial hypertrophy (e.g. aorta stenosis, etc.).
5. Patients with cardiogenic shock of any origin (except for acute miocardial infarction).
6. Patients with heart buffers of any origin (e.g. exudative pericarditis, etc.).
7. Patients with lung embolism.
8. Had long QT syndrome and other canopathies
1. is a common death in patients and, moreover, in people with chronic cardiovascular and respiratory diseases.

Sudden cardiac death (SCD)

1. severe weakness;
2. dizziness;

3. loss of consciousness,
4. the possible appearance of tonic contraction of skeletal muscles,
5. begins sharply with noisy breathing.

After 2.5-3 minutes, breathing stops altogether. It is important to remember that about three minutes after the onset of ventricle fibrillation or acidosis, irreversible changes occur in the cells of the brain's half cortex. In connection with such drastic changes in sudden heart death, timely diagnosis and a number of preventive measures (prescribing pharmacological drugs, endovascular treatment, interventional treatment within cardiovascular implantation) should be carried out. defibrillator). In such cases, the patient may first have cardiovascular or respiratory diseases, but death always occurs unexpectedly. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers the death in the presence of witnesses from 30 minutes to 5 hours into the middle after the onset of initial heart attacks to sudden heart death. One of the main causes of sudden heart death is divisions as well as abdominal fibrillation. We conditionally divided the frequency of patients' encounters by age and gender into 2 groups, according to the sudden heart death of the patients who complained, or the primary heart stop (Table 1). Patients between the ages of 48 and 68 in the first group, including 6 times more often among men than women, and patients between the ages of 69 and 87, had sudden cardiac death in the ratio of men and women to 4:1.

Clinical signs of the onset of sudden cardiac death.

1. Sudden loss of consciousness (75.2-96.8%)
2. Dizziness and nausea (73.8-98%)
3. Failure to detect pulse in major arteries (67.3-90.2%)
4. Changes in the color of the skin covers (66.7-74.8%)
5. Respiratory interruption or agonal type of respiration (60.8-75.7%)
6. Cessation of heart activity (64.9-83.7%)

Table 1

1. Despaation (57.8-67.0%)
2. Once tonic contraction of the body muscles (51.3-69.8%) was observed in patients.

Primary heart stoppage was observed mainly in the early morning hours and in the first half of the day. Patients did not experience clinical symptoms that were the basis for a diagnosis other than myocardial infarction, heart ischemic disease and nostalgic stenosis while mostly with a complaint. Mainly sudden heart death in the early hours of myocardial infarction, nostalgic stenosis, chronic heart it occurs in patients with deficiency and previously miocardial infarction and severe arthmetics, as well as people with cardiomegalia, Brugada syndrome and several HIV. Brugada's syndrome belongs to a group of autosom-dominant pedigree diseases that suddenly occur with fatal polymorphic abdominal tachycardia. At the age of 39-52, during sleep, syncope state and arrhythmia occur suddenly. The resulting embryo was ted to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it implanted. Symptoms of biological death in sudden cardiac death:

1. Enlargement of drafts and lack of exposure to light
2. Wheezing of a circular parchment
3. Bruises of the skin and mucous membranes
4. Inactivity of the nipples

5. The appearance of spots in the hand catalogue
6. Muscle loss

Conclusion: As a material of the scientific work, from 17.08.2022 to 12.04.2024, 247 patients were taken from the Khmer Rouge Regional Branch of the Regional Emergency Medical Center with atherosclerotic stenosis, heart ischemic disease, abdominal fibrillation. The age figure for patients was between 48 and 87 years old in men, their average age was 71.25, in women it was between 52 and 74 years old, and the average age figure was $66.18 \pm 1.1 \pm 1.4$. Since then, 169 (68.42%) of the patients were men and 78 (31.57%) were women. The diagnosis was based on patients' complaints when they arrived at the hospital, objective examination, anemia of the disease, as well as paraclinic information. We conditionally divided the frequency of patients' encounters by age and gender into 2 groups, according to the sudden heart death of the patients who complained, or the primary heart stop (Table 1). Patients between the ages of 48 and 68 in the first group, including 6 times more often among men than women, and patients between the ages of 69 and 87, had sudden cardiac death in the ratio of men and women to 4:1.

USEFUL LITERATURE:

1. History of diseases of the Department of Emergency Cardiology at the Khmer Rouge Regional Emergency Medical Center
2. Internal diseases. Selected lectures : textbook / . Konchalovsky [etc.] ; under the general editorship of P. Konchalovsky. — Moscow : Yurayt Publishing House, 2023. 497 p
3. Internal Diseases: Medical and Scientific Publication/ A.Gadayev.- Tashkent: Editor's Journal, 2022.
4. Shishkova V.N. Neuroprotection in patients with arterial hypertension: minimization of an unfavorable prognosis. Arch. – 2014; 8: 113–8.
5. Marshalko O. V., Karpovich A. I. Therapy: textbook : in 3 parts : [16+] / O. V. Marshalko, A. I. Karpovich. – 2nd ed., ster. – Minsk : RIPO, 2019. – Part 2. Cardiology. – 369 p
6. Internal Diseases: A Textbook for Cadets and Students of Higher Institutions. education in special." General Medicine". V 2 ch. Ch. 2 / Bova, Aleksandr Andreevich [i dr.] ; ed. by A. A. Bova. - Minsk: New Knowledge, 2020. - 816 p.

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7. Moiseev Valentin Sergeevich Editor: Moiseev Valentin Sergeevich, Martynov Anatoly Ivanovich, Mukhin Nikolay Alekseevich Publisher: GEOTAR-Media, 2019

8. Marshalko O. V., Karpovich A. I. Therapy: textbook : in 3 parts : [16+] / O. V. Marshalko, A. I. Karpovich. – 2nd ed., ster. – Minsk : RIPO, 2019. – Part 1. Pulmonology. – 205 p.

9. Internal diseases: a textbook for medical universities: in 2 volumes / ed. by S. I. Ryabov. – 5th ed., ispr. St. Petersburg: SpetsLit, 2015. – Volume 1. – 785 p.

10. Astvatsatryan A. V. Ostraya ischemiya myocarda i sokobylennye patologii [Acute myocardial ischemia and concomitant pathologies] : [16+] / A. V. Astvatsatryan. –Moscow; Berlin: Direct-Media, 2019. – 419 p.

11. Internal diseases in outpatient practice: a textbook for middle medical personnel / A. N. Smirnov, A. M. Granovskaya-Tsvetkova, E. V. Doskina [i dr.] ; ed. by A. N. Smirnov. – St. Petersburg : SpetsLit, 2014. – 368 p.

1 [https://www.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darsliklari/tibbiyot/Ichki%20kasalliklar%20\(Y.Arslonov,%20T.Nazarov\).pdf](https://www.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darsliklari/tibbiyot/Ichki%20kasalliklar%20(Y.Arslonov,%20T.Nazarov).pdf)

2 <https://fnkc-fmba.ru/zabolevaniya/vnezapnaya-serdechnaya-smert-vss/>

3 http://interdis.medped.tma.uz/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Ichki-kasalliklar_1-%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%B2%D0%B5%D1%80%D1%82%D0%B8%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%D0%BD.pdf

